

ROLE OF AYURVEDIC MEDICINE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PSYCHOTROPIC DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

Psychosis is a mental disorder characterized by a disconnection from reality. Psychosis is a group of disorder characterized by thought disorder, abnormal behaviour, defective cognition, delusion and hallucination. Adverse drug reaction is defined as any undesired or unintended effects of drugs treatment. According to the World Health Organization (WHO)- “adverse drug reaction (ADRs) has been defined one which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or modification of physiological function”. Adverse drug reactions are the most important causes of the mortality and morbidity. Antipsychotics are the most effective drugs which are used in the psychiatry in the maintenance therapy of mania, psychoses and schizophrenia. The antipsychotics drugs are

chemically disparate but have the common property of alleviating the symptoms of organic as well as functional psychosis. But they also have a capacity to cause a wide range of potential adverse drug reactions that can lead to non-compliance that can impair quality of life, may cause the extra pyramidal symptoms which can lead to discontinuation of therapy and in extreme cases it may be fatal. Knowledge of assessment of ADRs due to different antipsychotics is necessary. It helps to choose to safe treatment and reduce the risk of occurrence of ADRs by the clinicians. ADR are often poorly identified and reported in day-to-day medical practice. As we collect more and more information about ADRs, we need an active surveillance system regarding identification and reporting of ADRs with antipsychotic

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KEYWORDS: Antipsychotic Drugs, WHO, Adverse Drug Reactions, Ayurvedic plant, Psychiatrist.

INTRODUCTION

Neuropsychiatric disorders are a group of disorders that cause great morbidity and disability. Psychotic disorders are severe mental disorders that cause abnormal thinking and perceptions. Delusions and hallucinations are the two main symptoms of psychosis. People with psychosis may also lose touch with reality. Globally, the psychiatric disorder's prevalence is estimated at 6.7%. The symptoms of psychiatric disorders include anxiety, depression, eating disorders, autism spectrum, attention-deficit/hyperactivity, and conduct disorder. Different studies have been probed to clarify the basic molecular mechanism involved in such a disease's occurrence. Recently, it has been shown that early-life experiences can affect adulthood behaviour.^[1] Current medications for neuropsychiatric diseases mainly target disease symptoms. Therefore, there is a critical necessity to develop therapeutics which can delay, stop or reverse the progression of the condition.^[2] Nowadays, using medicinal plants as an alternative medication has been considered due to their biological safety.^[3] The discovery of drugs for the treatment of CNS disorders has faced some setbacks. Nervous system (NS) is vital to human body. In spite of the remarkable progress in knowledge of the CNS functions and structure, discovery of novel drugs along with their development for several central nervous system disorders have been challenging.^[4-6] Medicinal plants have been in use in health-care settings and have interestingly fostered the leads for drug development aimed at treating various diseases such as CND disorders, malaria, myeloma, inflammation, etc. *Bacopa monnieri*, *Centella asiatica*, *Curcuma longa*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Morinda citrifolia*, and *Withania somnifera* are among the most common plants used for treating CNS disorder.^[7]

Many medicinal plants have been studied and found to contain important compounds and substances, which may be further explored to assess their beneficial use in the management of disorders such as CNS disorders.^[8,9] *Papaver somniferum* L.), cannabis (the flowering or fruiting tops of any plant of the genus *Cannabis*, including *C. sativa* and its varieties) and cocaine (the major addictive ingredient in *Erythroxylon coca* and several species in the genus *Erythroxylum*) that were used for pain relief.^[10] A large population use ayurvedic medication both in single and compound form worldwide in psychosomatic diseases. In ayurveda, some examples of these diseases are Apasmara, Unmada, Smriti kshaya, Buddhi dourbalya, Manasa dosa, Bhrama, Anidra, Manodourbaly, Mada and Pralap.^[11] Normally these stress-induced physiological changes are adaptive, compensatory, and self-limiting but, when hectic conditions are regular, intense and override certain limits, these changes become quite unalterable and pathological in nature.^[12]

Current Situation: - Every year 10th October is the date when world mental health day is celebrated all over the world. The awareness regarding the balanced mental health is increasing and it is now recognized as a major cause of morbidity worldwide. As per WHO estimate, depression will be second only to cardiac diseases as the leading cause of morbidity and disability worldwide by 2020.^[13] India is, unfortunately, the leading country in adolescent and young age suicides. The condition is made worse by poor socio-economy, substance abuse, gender inequality and poor health infrastructure to deal with mental health issues. Unfortunately, India has got just 4000 psychiatrists for more than a billion populations. Further, in India, being a mentally ill patient carries huge stigma, this perhaps is the biggest of all barriers for mental treatment. Because of the stigma people don't prefer going to a mental health professional for an early evaluation.^[14-15] In a global study, India has been ranked 143rd among 188 countries on a range of health indicators including its poor performance on hygiene. However, India scored well for its better performance in areas like neglected tropical diseases including communicable diseases, overweight and harmful alcohol consumption.^[16] As India lags behind the world in medical professionals and spending on mental health issues, it is obvious that more than 60 million Indian populations suffer from mental disorder. Nearly 1-2% of its population suffers from severe mental disorders such as schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. About 5% of the population suffered from common mental disorders like depression and anxiety related problems as per the last report available in 2005. This data was recently quoted by Indian health and family welfare minister from national commission on macroeconomics and health forum. According to a

more recent report by National Mental Health Survey (NMHS) commissioned by Government of India and implemented and coordinated by National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences (NIMHANS), Bangalore, about 150 million Indians aged 18 and above and 7.3% of those aged 13 to 17 years of the total population are suffering from various mental disputes and are in need of mental care service.^[17-18]

Common Brain Disorders

Alzheimer's disease: -Alzheimer's disease (AD) was originally defined as presenile dementia and means an acquired mental disorder with loss of intellectual abilities to interfere with social or occupational functioning. It is associated with localized loss of neurons and brain shrinkage, mainly in the basal fore brain and hippocampus. The beta-amyloid peptide (BAP) plays a significant role in the development of AD. Although there is no cure for AD by synthetic drugs, but, to certain extent, it can be managed with them. Several studies have revealed that natural antioxidants, such as vitamin E, vitamin C, and beta-carotene are useful in scavenging free radicals generated during the progression of this disease. The loss of memory is considered to be the result of shortage of a nerve transmitter, acetylcholine. By inhibiting the activity of the enzyme, acetyl cholinesterase, which splits or breaks down the transmitter substance, it is possible to increase the level of this transmitter in the brain. Synthetic drugs that inhibit the breakdown of the messenger or transmitter acetylcholine, may delay the development of the disease.^[19-20]

Depression: - Depression is a common affective disorder of mood rather than disturbances of thought or cognition. It is the most common affective disorder which is accompanied by delusions and hallucination. In this disease condition, the neurotransmitters levels such as dopamine, acetylcholine, nor epinephrine etc., in the brain are increased. The symptoms of this disease are of two types (i) biological symptoms: retardation of thought, loss of libido, sleep disturbance and loss of appetite (ii) emotional symptoms: feelings of guilt, loss of motivation, ugliness etc. There are 2 types of depressive syndrome e.g., (i) unipolar depression: mood swinging always in the same direction; (ii) bipolar depression: depression alternates with mania.^[21]

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD): - It is considered as a disorder of children but it is not limited to them. In fact, 30- 70% of kids with this disorder, continue showing symptoms of ADHD when they grow up. In addition, people who were never diagnosed ADHD in childhood may develop more obvious symptoms when grown up,

causing trouble on the job or in relationships. In people with ADHD, the neurotransmitters are less active in areas of the brain that control attention. It is exactly not known what causes this chemical imbalance, but it is thought that genes may play a role as this disorder often runs in families. It has been found that adults given stimulants have fewer ADHD symptoms and some of them may feel better concentration, but complete cure is often not seen.^[22]

Anxiety: -anxiety is a psychological and physiological state characterized by cognitive, somatic, emotional, and behavioral factors. These factors combine to create an unpleasant feeling that is typically associated with fear, worry or uneasiness. Without an identifiable triggering stimulus, anxiety is a generalized mood state. In fact, it is distinguished from fear, which occurs in the presence of an external threat. As such, anxiety is the result of threats that are perceived to be uncontrollable or unavoidable whereas fear is related to the specific behaviors of avoidance and escape.^[23]

Migraine: - Migraine prevalence studies have indicated that more than 17 percent of the female and six percent of the male population in the United States suffer from the condition. In addition to the weakening effect of a migraine attack, sufferers report a significant impact on their quality of life between attacks. Many migraine patients report that the fear of getting a headache completely disrupts their capacity to plan social events, vacations, and other family activities. Available research on the treatment of migraine focuses on acute treatment and prophylactic medications. Advances in acute treatment are well established. In contrast, there has been restricted progression in the prophylactic treatment of migraine. Herbal drug approaches to migraine prevention have shown some oath.^[24]

Severe Mental illness: Schizophrenia and related psychotic disorders are a group of severe mental illnesses. In severe mental illness, a person has mental health problems that are persistent, result in moderate to severe disability and may require treatment for long time. One of the ways in which mental health problems, in severely mentally ill persons manifest is psychosis. Psychosis is a psychiatric condition in which a person has hallucinations, delusions, disorganised behaviour and impaired reality testing. Hallucinations are false perceptions without any stimulus which means s/he may perceive something that does not exist in reality e.g., s/he may start hearing voices of people talking when there is no one around. These can occur in all five senses like sound, sight, smell, touch and taste and are called auditory, visual, olfactory, tactile and gustatory hallucinations. Delusions are firmly held false beliefs that cannot be corrected by any amount of reasoning or evidence to the

contrary. These beliefs cannot be explained by the person's educational, social and cultural background. Delusions may be of many types e.g. delusion of persecution, grandiosity etc. Persons with psychosis are unaware that their experiences could be imaginary and they cannot differentiate real from unreal. There is severe disturbance in social and personal functioning.

Pharmacological treatment: The current guidelines that address pharmacologic treatment of severe mental illness fall into one of four categories, according to their scope and the stringency with which they rely on empirical evidence: recommendations, comprehensive treatment options, medication algorithms, and expert consensus. The first category, recommendations, is exemplified by the Patient Outcomes Research Team (PORT) treatment recommendations for schizophrenia.^[25] Comprehensive treatment options Practice guidelines in the second category have been developed pre dominantly by professional organizations. These guidelines are comprehensive in the scope of therapeutic options presented Pharmacologic treatment is ad dressed in detail by practice guide lines for the treatment of patients with bipolar disorder.^[26] schizo phrenia.^[27] major depressive disorder.^[28] panic disorder.^[29] developed by the American Psychiatric Association (APA) and practice guidelines for the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) developed by the International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies (ISTSS).^[30]

Classification of Drugs

On the basis of the purpose of their use, different drugs can be classified into followings

- Therapeutic Drugs
- Psychoactive Drugs

Although both of these categories; often overlap. Due to the specific usage and wide range, psychoactive drugs are treated as a distinct class.

Therapeutic Drugs

A Therapeutic drug is a substance that has healing or preventive properties in relation to certain diseases, or is administered to enable a medical diagnosis. The drugs in common therapeutic use that may be classified chiefly into following four categories

1. **Analgesics and Antipyretics:** - An analgesic is a type of drug that relieves pain. E.g. Aspirin and Paracetamol.

2. **Antihistaminic:** - These are the drugs which antagonize the action of histamine. These are commonly used in allergic disorders and other conditions like common cold. E.g. Chlo cyclizine.
3. **Antidepressants:** - These are the drugs which are generally used in psychiatric disorders to treat the endogenous depression. These drugs have an initial sedative effect which is followed by an antidepressant effect within a week or more. Commonly used antidepressant drugs are: Imipramine, Amitriptyline, etc.
4. **Tranquilizers:** - These are the drugs that produce a general tranquility without the impairment of high- thinking facilities or the inducement of a sleep. To reduce tension and anxiety of mental patients Tranquilizers like reserpine and chlorpromazine are useful.

Psychoactive Drugs

A psychoactive drug, psycho-pharmaceutical or psychotropic drug is a chemical substance that acts principally upon the central nervous system where it affects brain function, resulting in modification in perception, mood, consciousness, cognition and behaviour.

Classification

Generally used psychoactive drugs are: -

Narcotics, stimulants, Hallucinogens, Depressants

Narcotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opium • Morphine • Heroin
Depressants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barbiturates • Tranquilizers
Stimulants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amphetamine • Cocaine
Hallucinogens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LSD • Charas, Ganja • Mescaline

Fig. 1: Classification of psychoactive drugs and their examples.

Fig. 2: Common narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

A. Opium pod showing dried opium. B. Dried opium pod. C. Curde opium. D. Opium sticks. E. Opium pellets. F. Burnt opium powder after smoking.

1) Narcotics

This group comprises of substances that act on the CNS and bring relief from discomfort and produce sleep. The origin of most narcotics is opium; a sticky milky juice obtained from the unripe pod of poppy. Example: Opium, morphine, heroin, codeine, synthetic opiates, etc.

- **Morphine** is obtained from raw opium. It is normally administered by injection. It results in a euphoric state, with sleepy and relaxed appearance of the user. It is generally 3 to 5 times stronger than opium.

- **Heroin** (diacetylmorphine) is a white crystalline powder, which is derivative by adding two acetyl groups to the morphine, found in the opium. Heroin in impure form is known as Brown Sugar. It is 10-15 times more effective than morphine. It may be either injected or sniffed to cause similar effects as that of opium and heroin but with higher magnitude.

- **Codeine** is also a byproduct of morphine but is less effective as analgesic. It acts as a base in many pain relievers and cough remedies.

Fig. 3: Common narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

A. Morphine powder, ranges in colour from offwhite to dark brown.

B. Crude morphine C. Morphine tablets. D. Morphine ampoules.

2) Stimulants ("uppers"): Stimulants consist of substances that, stimulates the mind, wakes one up and euphoria (a feeling of well-being), but do not affect perception. These drugs are also referred in the terminology of "speed".

Examples: Amphetamines, methamphetamines, caffeine, nicotine, cocaine, etc.

3) Hallucinogens: It includes psychedelics, dissociatives and deliriant. This category comprises all those substances that produce distinct alterations in normal thought processes, perceptions and mood. There are a number of substances with varying chemical compositions that have hallucinogenic properties.

Examples: LSD (lysergic acid diethylamide), PCP (phencyclidine), DMT (dimethyltryptamine), mescaline, psilocybin, etc.

Fig. 4: A. Pure cocaine. B. Peyote Cactus (active compound mescaline).

B. Lysergic Acid Diethylamide (LSD 25). D. L.S.D in the form of pills.

4) Depressants ("downers"), including sedatives, hypnotics, and narcotics. This category consists of all of the sleep inducing, calmative, anxiety-reducing, anesthetizing substances, which induces perceptual changes like dream sequences, and also often bring to the mind the feelings of euphoria.

Examples: Alcoholic beverages (ethanol), barbiturates, benzodiazepines, etc.

Ayurvedic treatment

Natural herbs: Natural herbs are plant-based products used for culinary flavoring, medicinal purposes, and overall health maintenance. They include leaves, flowers, roots, or bark used fresh or dried in teas, tinctures, capsules, or salves.

Traditional medicine is "the knowledge, skills and practices based on the theories, beliefs and experiences indigenous to different cultures, used in the maintenance of health and in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness".^[31] There are many different systems of traditional medicine and the philosophy and practices of each are influenced by the prevailing conditions, environment, and geographic area within which it first evolved,^[31] however, a common philosophy is a holistic approach to life, equilibrium of the mind, body, and the environment, and an emphasis on health rather than on disease. Generally, the focus is on the overall condition of the individual, rather than on the particular ailment or disease from which the patient is suffering, and the use of herbs is a core part of all systems of traditional medicine.^[32]

Use of herbs and other substances: Natural materials such as plants and plant-based compounds have been used for functional, therapeutic, medicinal, and prophylactic applications against various illnesses.^[33-34] Complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) practices make use of natural substances such as foods, herbs, minerals, fungal and animal products, megavitamins, and non-vitamin supplements, including using them in the practices of traditional medicine which may integrate other CAM or non-CAM methods^[35-36-37] for the treatment of diseases, including CNS disorders. Typical examples include the therapeutic claims for ginseng, flaxseed oil, echinacea, *Moringa oleifera* extracts, glucosamine, Omega-3 fatty acid, fish oil, and nonvitamin supplements. Herbal medicines, also known as phytotherapy, comprise not only usage of plants and their products but could also include using mineral and animal products often in combination with plants. Herbal medicine is part of the major branches of CAM with commercial success, and includes elixirs, powders, and

tablets, which are usually available in the form of nutritional supplements. Some herbal medicines have demonstrated to have efficacy in the treatment of diseases such as CNS disorders which often rely on the bioactive compounds present in them. Bioactive compounds have been described and studied in many natural products for various reasons and can be tapped for exploration against CNS-related diseases.^[38-39] Little regulation exists regarding the safety and standards of herbal medicines. Caution should be taken, as many natural products also contain toxic substances and even allergens.^[40]

Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*): Brahmi as an add-on to olanzapine has shown better efficacy, significant improvement in psychopathology was seen after one month. Brahmi is extensively used in Ayurveda practice either independently or in combination with other herbs in various mental health conditions.^[41] Preclinical trials have demonstrated the antioxidant properties of Brahmi extracts on the brain, which could potentially lead to its positive effect on mental function. It has been reported to enhance kinase activity, restore synaptic activity, ultimately enhancing neural transmission in the brain thus repairing damaged neurons. Being a nootropic, its nootropic properties have been reported to be possibly mediated by its constituent saponins, bacosides A and B through glutamatergic mechanism.^[42]

Fig. 5: *Bacopa monnieri*.

Khat (*Catha edulis*): Khat refers to the evergreen shrub *Catha edulis* indigenous to East Africa. Khat also refers to the leaves and shoots of the plant chewed to provide mild stimulant effects. Khat has a variety of regional names such as mairungi (Uganda), miraa (Kenya), qat (Yemen), or tschat (Ethiopia and Somalia). The shrub is an intensively cultivated, high-income cash crop in East Africa and the southwestern part of the Arabian Peninsula. In addition to supplying domestic markets, fresh khat bundles, each weighing 250-300 g, are nowadays shipped by airfreight into Europe, Australia and North America to ethnic groups immigrated from countries where khat-chewing is a tradition.^[43-44] Several types of compounds have been isolated from khat, including amino acids, ascorbic acid, flavonoids,

phenylalkylamine alkaloids, sesquiterpene polyester alkaloids (cathedulins), steroids, tannins, and terpenoids. The main psychoactive constituent was identified in 1975 and named cathinone.^[45] The cathinone-content of the leaves typically ranges from 0.04 to 0.3 %. Cathinone is a chemically unstable aminoketone. Khat and its main ingredients are amphetamine-like dopaminergic psychostimulants with peripheral sympathomimetic effects.^[46,47] In the central nervous system, cathinone inhibits the reuptake of dopamine and norepinephrine into presynaptic nerve terminals without affecting serotonin transport.^[48]

Fig. 6: *Catha edulis*.

Mushrooms (*Agaricus bisporus*): mushrooms, also called “magic mushrooms”, are the psychotropic fungus containing psilocybin and psilocin (Fig. 1). At low dosage, the main effects of magic mushrooms are perceptual distortions and changes of thought or mood. They are categorized into three major subsets based on their chemical structures, including indole alkylamines or tryptamines (e.g. psilocybin and psilocin), phenethylamines such as mescaline and methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA).^[49] The major adverse effects of magic mushrooms are associated with the central nervous system and sympathomimetic effects vary greatly between individuals and the duration time of use.^[50] People may have the feelings of relaxation, dizziness, euphoria, visual disturbances, delusions, illusion, or real hallucinations. Other adverse effects include restlessness, incoordination, anxiety, and faint judgments of time or distance etc. but in general, body temperature remains normal. Users may use 'bad trips' to describe their panic reactions and psychosis-like states. However, apparent physical symptoms have been recorded such as severe stomach pain, persistent vomiting, and diarrhoea.^[51]

Fig. 7: *Agaricus bisporus*.

Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*): Ashwagandha, a foreign Indian herb. Its root has noteworthy stress-relieving properties equivalent to those of powerful drugs used to treat depression and anxiety. Additionally, it has outstanding defensive effects on the nervous system.^[52] Ashwagandha extract (WSE) has reduced symptom exacerbation, anxiety, and depression in schizophrenia patients in two randomized controlled trials. Previous pre-clinical and clinical trials have confirmed potent anti-inflammatory, immunomodulating, and antioxidant properties of WSE.^[53] In addition, WSE has also shown beneficial effects for anxiety, stress, and depression in separate clinical trials. WSE may restore the disturbed immune-inflammatory homeostasis and poor antioxidant defences rearing dysfunctional neural circuits and alterations in neurotransmitters associated with depression and anxiety symptoms in schizophrenia.^[54]

Fig. 8: *Withania somnifera*.

Tagara (*Valeriana wallichii*): Tagara has also been shown to improve schizophrenia symptoms when compared to placebo but it was not statistically significant. The sedative effect of valerian is proven by previous clinical trials. Valepotriates are potent chemical constituents present in valerian responsible for this action.^[55] Animal experiments had proven the antioxidant and neuroprotective properties of the drug.^[56]

Fig. 9: *Veleriana wallichii*.

Jatamansi (*Nardostachys jatamansi*)

It helps to promote physical and mental health; it also shows marked tranquillizing activity. As Medications for anxiety viz benzodiazepines, MAOI's have limitations due to unbearable side effects. Herbal anxiolytics promise to alleviate anxiety and other psychiatric disorders with minimal adverse effects. It has its anxiolytic activity.^[57] The roots and the rhizome extracts (ethanolic) and its fraction have been studied for improvement of cognition, antidepressant, anticonvulsant, ant Parkinson's, and no tropic activities and neuroprotective activities.^[58–59]

Fig. 10: *Nardostachys jatamansi*.

Yashtimadhu (*Glycyrrhizin glabra*)

This suggests that antidepressant-like effect of liquorice extract seems to be mediated by increase of brain norepinephrine and dopamine, but not by increase of serotonin. Monoamine oxidase inhibiting effect of liquorice may be contributing favorably to the antidepressant-like activity. Thus, it is concluded that liquorice extract may possess an antidepressant-like effect.^[60]

Fig. 11: *Glycyrrhizin glabra*.**Shankpushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*)**

Its whole plant usage is as a wonderful brain tonic which aids in improving its ability and capacity and for rejuvenating nervous functions. It enhances learning, memory, intelligence, concentration level and the ability to recall. In traditional medicine, it is used in the treatment of disorders such as hypertension, anxiety, neurosis, stress, insomnia.^[61]

Fig. 12: *Convolvulus pluricaulis*.

Lavandula angustifolium (Lavender): - Lavender is used basically as an aromatic essential oil for relaxation. In a single-blind randomized control trial, 80 women who took daily baths with lavender oil experienced improved mood, reduced aggression, and a more positive outlook.^[62] Likewise, the combination of lavender (60 drops/day of a Lavandula tincture) and imipramine (100 mg/day) was found to be more effective in the treatment of depression than either treatment alone, according to a double-blind randomized control trial. The findings of this study suggested that taking a moderate amount of lavender might help reduce the number of tricyclic antidepressants required to treat depression, leading to fewer side effects.^[63]

Fig. 13: *Lavender*.

Psychactive natural products: Psychoactive natural products are plant, fungi or animal derived compounds that alter brain function, affecting mood, perception and behavior.

Table 1: Chronology of selected psychoactive natural products.^[64]

S.No	Plant Name	Original or common sources (s)	Active principle	isolation	Psychoactivity type
1	<i>Opium poppy</i>	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Morphin	1805	narcotic-sedative
2	<i>Coffee plant, Tea plant, Kolanut, Guarana</i>	<i>Coffea arabica, Camellia sinensis, Cola nitida, Paulinia spp.</i>	Caffein	1820	stimulant
3	<i>Tobacco, Duboisia</i>	<i>Nicotiana tabacum, Duboisia spp.</i>	Nicotine	1828	Stimulant
4	<i>Belladonna, Angel's trumpet, Datura / Thorn apple</i>	<i>Atropa, Brugmansia, Datura, Duboisia spp</i>	Hyoscyamine	1833	Hallucinogen/narcotic
5	<i>Syrian rue, Ayahuasca vine</i>	<i>Peganum harmala, Banisteriopsis caapi</i>	Harmala alkaloids	1841-1885	hallucinogen/sedative, monoamine oxidase inhibitor
6	<i>Coca plant, Colombian coca</i>	<i>Erythroxylum coca, E. novo granatense</i>	Cocaine	1860	Stimulant
7	<i>Kava</i>	<i>Piper methysticum</i>	Kavalactones	1860-1959	Anxiolytic/sedative
8	<i>Ma huang (Ephedra)</i>	<i>Ephedra equisetina (ma huang) and other Ephedra spp.</i>	Ephedrine	1887	Stimulant
9		<i>Bufo toads; Anadenanthera trees</i>	Bufotenine	1893	hallucinogen
10	<i>Peyote, San Pedro cactus</i>	<i>Lophophora williamsii, Echinopsis (Trichocereus) spp.</i>	Mescaline	1896	hallucinogen
11	<i>Iboga</i>	<i>Tabernanthe iboga</i>	Ibogaine	1901	Stimulant/hallucinogen
12	<i>Kratom</i>	<i>Mitragyna speciosa</i>	Mitragynine	1921	Stimulant/sedative
13	<i>Magic mushrooms,</i>	<i>Psilocybe (Stropharia), Conocybe, Inocybe, Paneolus spp.</i>	Psilocybin	1958	hallucinogen
14	<i>Mimosa</i>	<i>Dictyoloma, Piptadenia and Mimosa spp.; Bufo alvarius</i>	5-MeO-DMT	1959	Hallucinogen

Table 2: Potential Ayurvedic plants cure most of the mental conditions.^[65]

S. No	Botanical Name	Family	Hindi Name	English Name	Major chemical compounds	Ayurvedic recommendations
1	<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i>	Acanthaceae	Adusa Adus, Safed vasa	Malabar nut	Vasicine, Vasicinone	Its powder with honey cures old epilepsy disease
2	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Liliaceae	Pyaz, Kanda	Onion	Di alkenyl sulfides	Tea from its seeds is beneficial in insomnia.
3	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Plantaginaceae	Brahmi	Thyme leaved gratiola, Indian	Bacosides A, B, C	It's juice is taken with "kuth"

				pennywort		(Costus speciosus root) powder in honey to help in hysteria it's also recommended by adding "kuth" and "shankhapushpi" to cure epilepsy and hysteria. It's very useful in the recovery of memory power.
4	<i>Brassica nigra</i>	Brassicaceae	Rae	Black mustard	Gallic acid, quercetin	Its seeds and pigeon's droppings after grinding, are applied on forehead. It relieves migraine.
5	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> Linn	Cannabaceae	Bhang	Marijuana	Tetrahydrocannabinoids	Its leaves along with asafoetida have been used for epilepsy type problem in women. It's also useful in treating insomnia.
6	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	Rutaceae	Neembu, Kagaji nimbu	Lemon	Bergamottin, bergapten	Lemon juice is given to the patient of anxiety to normalize the heartbeat
7	<i>Convolvulus microphyllus</i>	Convolvulaceae	Shankhapushpi, Shankahuli	Shankhapushpi	Convuloline, convolamine	Its powder is mixed with milk or honey and "ghee" and taken to improve to the memory power.
8	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Apiaceae	Dhania	Coriander	Linalool, geranyl acetate	When its extract is regularly taken, the vertigo and headache is relieved.
9	<i>Cyperus scariosus</i>	cyperaceae	Nagarmotha	Nutgrass	Cyperene, Patchouli alcohol	It cures epilepsy when given with cow milk.
10	<i>Datura metel</i>	Solanaceae	Dhaturo	Thorn apple	Hyoscine, hyoscyamine	Its seeds are ground with black pepper and given for treating psychosis.

11	<i>Daucus carota</i>	Apiaceae	Gajar	Carrot	Carotenoids, alpha-Pinene, sabinene	Leaves are extracted with warm "ghee" and drops given in nose and ears to cure migraine through sneezing.
12	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Moraceae	Bargad, Badha	Banyan tree	Benghalenosi des, Leucopelargo nidin glycoside	Its root bark powder when taken in sugar and cow's milk, improves memory power.
13	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	Peepal	Peepal tree, Sacred	Pelargonidine glycosides, sterols	Extract of branches cures madness.
14	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Papilionaceae	Mulethi	Fig, Liquorice root	Phenolics, glabridin	Root powder in ghee brings enhancements in epilepsy.
15	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Asteraceae	Hurhul	Sunflower	Diterpenoids, Kaurenoic acid	Its leaves juice and seeds are grinded together and applied on forehead to get relief from migraine.
16	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Sahijan, Munga	Drum stick plant	Moringine, Moringinine	Decoction of its roots is given for epilepsy.
17	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i>	Valerianaceae	Jatamansi, Balchhad	Spikenard	Jatamansone and terpenoids	It's useful in epilepsy when taken with "ghee". "Jatamansi", "bach" and "Brahmi" juice are mixed in honey and given in mental problem.
18	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Papaveraceae	Posta, Post, Afeem	Poppy, Opium	Morphine, codeine, thebaine, papaverine	Poppy is beneficial in delirium, sleeplessn ess, convulsion, etc.
19	<i>Piper longum</i>	Piperaceae	Peepal	Long pepper	Piperine, Piperlongumine	Its roots in jaggery are given to overcome insomnia. admixture of "Peepal" and "bach" are given

						in milk to cure migraine pain.
20	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Myrtaceae	Amrud, Safari	Guava	Oleanolic acid, ursolic acid	Decoction of leaves is given to cure mental and physical deformities. Tinge of leaves is massaged on the backbone of children for convulsion
21	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Punicaceae	Anar	Pomegranate	1-(2-propenyl)-piperidine in leaves, anthocyanins in fruit.	Leaves after boiling with water and concentrating, the extract is given in warm milk to cure fatigue, tiredness and insomnia. Leaves and rose flowers are cooked in water and concentrated. It's given in ghee to cure madness.
22	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i>	Sapindaceae	Reetha	Soapnut tree	Triterpenoid, sesquiterpenoid, saponin, glycosides	Its fruits are ground with black pepper and few drops poured in the nostrils to get relief from migraine pain. Its seeds along with kernel and peel are ground and to be inhaled regularly to cure epilepsy, fully.
23	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Myrtaceae	Lavang, Laung	Clove	Carvarol, thymol, eugenol	Cloves are grinded in water and the paste is applied on the earlobes to cure migraine.
24	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Vitaceae	Munakka, Angur, Dakh	Grapevine, Resins	Glycosides of pelargonidin cyanidin	"Munakka" is roasted and given for dizziness.
25	<i>Zizyphus mauritiana</i>	Rhamnaceae	Ber	Jujube	Peptide and cyclopeptide alkaloids, sanjoinine	Although not prescribed in Ayurveda, its fruit is used in

						mental healing as scientifically proved
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The prominent role of natural products, alkaloids specially, in the development of psychopharmacology, new plant-derived psychoactive drugs are lacking. Advantages of natural products over synthetic compounds for interacting with biological systems of therapeutic interest have been repeatedly documented. Advantages of ethnopharmacology-driven plant collections over the biodiversity or chemotaxonomy-oriented ones have also been reported.

The main focus of this review is to discuss the advantages to incorporate ethnopharmacology data into the research design in order to optimize the identification of innovative drugs for neurological and mental illnesses.

The advantages of screening natural products over synthetic molecules for drug discovery have been advocated over decades and recently reviewed. From a chemical point of view, the advantages of natural products include (a) having a wide range and high degree of stereochemistry pharmacophores, resulting in not only bioactivity but likelihood to reach the site of action; (b) they characteristically fit the molecular chemical descriptors adequate for bioactivity; (c) they probe a different, wider, and more drug-like chemical space than the scaffolds present among commercial drugs; (d) they cover parts of chemical characteristics of bioactivity targets that medicinal chemistry compounds do not; and (e) the vast majority of all drugs have a close match natural product.^[66-67]

Despite well-known examples of plant-derived drugs, such as morphine from a poppy or vincristine and vinblastine from the Madagascar periwinkle, only about 200 of the 10,000–15,000 higher plants with reported medicinal properties are taken advantage of in Western medicine.^[68-69]

Traditional medical systems are organized as cultural systems.^[70] and may greatly differ in the meanings of health, disease, disease etiologies, and cure.^[71] resulting in medicinal practices not easily accommodated into the biomechanical paradigm of contemporary Western medicine. On top of the expected differences in the understanding/beliefs of what causes the condition, the very description of psychiatric symptomatology varies in different cultures.^[72] Traditional pharmaceutical techniques also bring insights on the best choice for

extraction and isolation procedures, by narrowing the possibilities and thus decreasing the workload. For instance, one can expect components of essential oils to be the active compounds in aromatic teas (where the plant is added to hot water for a few minutes), while thermally sensitive compounds can be excluded from nonaromatic teas (where the plant is added to cold water and then boiled). In the case of drugs active at the central nervous system (CNS), one must be attentive to the presence of alkaloids (as free bases, glycosides, salts of primary, secondary, tertiary amines, or quaternary ammonium salts) and explore 9:1 or 1:1 water/ethanol extracts for remedies prepared as bottles in wine or distilled spirit.^[73]

As allopathic drugs, traditional remedies are used following specific instructions and for varying periods of time. In pharmacodynamic terms, it is expected that long term use may have effects significantly different than acute (single administration) or sub-chronic (few administrations) challenge in any given molecular target. The correspondence between traditional use and its laboratory investigation collides with practical matters, such as the need for higher amounts of compounds/extracts/fraction for *in vivo*, orally administered, and/or repeated administration. Needless to say, that for CNS drugs, this issue is of utmost importance since it has been established that the long-term effects on initial targets are often required to achieve a new functional state.^[74]

As India's most ancient and traditional system of medicine, Ayurveda has its unique identity. Ayurveda views life as a blend of senses, mind, body, and soul. Ayurveda is concerned with spiritual, emotional, and social well-being as well as bodily diseases. Ayurveda is regarded as "The Science of Life" and entails treating a person's physical, emotional, and spiritual well-being. Manas (mind), Atma (soul), and Shareware the three foundations of life (body). Ayurvedic psychiatry connects the mind, body, and soul. As a result, Ayurveda is a high-quality; philosophy and system for treating the entire person, body and mind, and holistic science of health and longevity.^[75] Substantial imbalances can perturb mental state and a psychological illness, causes bodily functioning to be disrupted.

The connection between mind and body is essential in Ayurveda. In Ayurveda, total health is defined as a perfect balance of mind, body, and spirit. Since the pre-Vedic period, ancient India has had a concept of mind. The mind has been conceptualized as a functioning component of ATMAN (soul), as described in the Vedas, the first written literature of the human race. Thoughts govern facial appearance, and beliefs influence facial expression, according to the Vedas. The mental imbalance was mentioned in Charaka Samhita as well as

in Ashtanga Hridaya.^[76] In Ayurveda, total health is defined as the ideal balance of mind, body, and spirit. Satwawajay Chikitsa, Yuktivyapashray Chikitsa, and Daivyapashray Chikitsa are the three elements of Ayurveda's therapy methods. In Ayurveda, Sattvavajaya treatment is mentioned in the Charaka Samhita and is a new notion of psychotherapy. Daivyapashraya is a religious therapy, whereas Yuktivyapashraya is a rational therapy.^[77] Manas, the outside mind, absorbs sensory experiences from our sense perception and classifies them; nonetheless, it is still unsure of their actual nature. Buddha is the one who clarifies, evaluates, and provides a definitive comprehension of things. As a result, whereas Ahamkara, the Ego, self-appropriates the observed for its own impressions, Manas assimilates Buddhi and sense sensations define them. Buddhi describes them, makes distinctions amongst them, and condenses them into ideas. Therefore, its goal is to offer distinctiveness and clarity in knowledge.

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive review highlights that antipsychotic drug, while essential for managing psychoses and related psychiatric disorders, carry a significant burden of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) that can compromise patient compliance, quality of life, and even prove fatal. This necessitates robust pharmacovigilance and active surveillance systems to identify, report, and mitigate these risks. Concurrently, Ayurvedic medicine offers a promising complementary or alternative avenue through a wide array of medicinal plants—such as *Bacopa monnieri*, *Withania somnifera*, *Nardostachys jatamansi* and *Glycyrrhiza glabra* which demonstrate neuroprotective, anxiolytic, antidepressant, and cognition-enhancing properties with potentially fewer adverse effects. The integration of traditional ethnopharmacological knowledge with modern scientific validation could bridge existing treatment gaps, particularly in resource-limited settings like India, where mental health infrastructure is strained. However, rigorous clinical trials, standardized formulations, and safety assessments are imperative before widespread clinical adoption. Ultimately, a collaborative, evidence-based approach combining the strengths of allopathic and Ayurvedic systems may optimize therapeutic outcomes for the growing population affected by neuropsychiatric disorders worldwide.

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